

How to use TARNAS

The instructions to download and install TARNAS can be retrieved from

<https://github.com/bdslab/TARNAS>

in the files `INSTALL.txt` and `README.md`. The distribution of TARNAS includes two versions, a GUI and a CLI, a subfolder named `examples`, which contains three subfolders: `TransExamples`, `Abstractions` and `QuantitativeFeatures`, which are the running examples of the paper

Michela Quadrini, Piero Hierro Canchari, Piermichele Rosati, and Luca Tesei, “TARNAS: A Tool for Translating and Abstracting RNA Secondary Structures”, 2025.

This is a support file for the paper, providing instructions on possible user scenarios. The `examples` folder is also included in this Zenodo document.

Instructions to use the CLI version of TARNAS 1.0

RNA secondary structure translations scenario. To translate molecules represented in a supported format into another format, you can use the CLI version of TARNAS:

```
>java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar <inputPath> <outputPathFolder> translate <DEST_FORMAT>
```

where `<inputPath>` is the path of file to transform or the folder containing the molecule files to transform, `<outputPath>` is the path of the output folder and `<DEST_FORMAT>` is the selected format for translation of molecules. All molecules in the input folder must be represented in the same format.

For example, to translate molecules represented as XML files and stored in the XML folder into the BPSEQ format, you can use the CLI version of TARNAS:

```
> java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar examples/TransExamples/XML examples/TransExamples/BPSEQ  
translate BPSEQ
```

The RNA secondary structures in the XML folder were generated using the RNAVIEW tool on the PDB file of 5S ribosomal RNA, as listed in the file `list_pdbID_5S.txt`

Additionally, during the translation process, the user can choose not to include the molecular header and can generate sequence and structural information using the following two commands:

```
> java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar <inputPath> <outputPathFolder> translate <DEST_FORMAT>
--no-header
```

```
> java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar <inputPath> <outputPathFolder> translate <DEST_FORMAT>
--statistics
```

Deleting or retaining comments, blank lines and headers of the file. We can also clean files by removing comments, blank lines, and lines containing a specific “word” by running the following commands.

To remove comments:

```
> java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar <inputPath> <outputPathFolder> cleaning --comments
```

To remove empty lines:

```
> java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar <inputPath> <outputPathFolder> cleaning --empty
```

To remove lines containing a specific word (replace <word> with the word you want to delete):

```
> java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar <inputPath> <outputDirectoryPath> cleaning
--lines=<word>
```

Only for molecules formalized in DB and DB no sequence, TARNAS allows the user to merge sequences that are split across multiple line by running:

```
> java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar <inputPath> <outputPathFolder> cleaning --merge
```

Abstracting RNA secondary structures into three views: core, core Plus and shape. In addition to format translation and file cleaning, TARNAS computes RNA secondary structure abstractions called Core, Core Plus and Shape, by the following commands, respectively:

```
> java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar <inputPath> <outputPathFolder> abstractions --core
```

```
> java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar <inputPath> <outputPathFolder> abstractions --coreplus
```

```
> java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar <inputPath> <outputPathFolder> abstractions --shape
```

where <inputPath> is the path of file to transform or the folder containing the molecule files to transform, <outputPath> is the path of the output folder and <DEST_FORMAT> is the selected format for translation of molecules. The molecules into the input folder need to be represented in the same dot-bracket format.

For our example, we have determined:

- Core by running

```
>java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar examples/TransExamples/DB examples/TransExamples/Core
abstractions -core
```

- Core Plus by running

```
>java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar examples/TransExamples/DB examples/TransExamples/Core
abstractions -corePlus
```

- Shape by running

```
>java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar examples/TransExamples/DB examples/TransExamples/Core
abstractions -shape
```

The user can obtain the three abstractions by using one of the two equivalent command

```
> java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar <inputPath> <outputDirectoryPath> abstractions --core
--coreplus --shape
```

```
> java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar <inputPath> <outputDirectoryPath> abstractions
```

The user can also choose to save the result as zip file by considering the extra options, `-zip`,

```
> java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar <inputPath> <outputDirectoryPath> --zip <zipFileName>
translate DB
```

```
> java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar <inputPath> <outputDirectoryPath> --zip <zipFileName>
cleaning --comments
```

```
> java -jar TARNAS_CLI.jar <inputPath> <outputDirectoryPath> --zip <zipFileName>
abstractions
```

Instructions to use the GUI versions

The home page of the TARNAS Standalone version is shown in Figure 1.

RNA secondary structure translations scenario

Figure 1: home page of the TARNAS Standalone version

Step 1. In the first step of this scenario, the user can upload an RNA secondary structure or a set of structures. This can be done by using the "ADD FILE" button to upload a single file or the "ADD FOLDER" button to upload a folder containing the structures. Uploaded data can be removed by clicking the "Remove" button or viewed in the text area after clicking the "Preview" button. Figure 2 shows a screen of the TARNAS Standalone version after uploading some molecules.

Step 2. In this step, the user can choose whether to include the header and non-canonical base pairs by selecting the additional options: "include reader" to add the header, and "generate non canonical pairs". Moreover, the user can also decide to generate some sequence and structural information by the additional option "generate statistics" and the output format in the dropdown menu.

Step 3. To start the transformation of secondary structure, the "Run" button should be clicked.

Deleting or retaining comments, blank lines and header of the file.

Step 1. In the first step of this scenario, a user should upload the RNA secondary structure provided in a supported format as described in Step 1 of *RNA secondary structure translations scenario*.

Step 2. In this step, the user can choose to remove all comments, lines containing a particular word or empty lines by selecting the relative option. If the user intends to delete lines containing a particular word, it is necessary to specify the word in the box. Additionally, TARNAS allows the user to merge sequences that are split across multiple lines in both the DB and DB no sequence formats.

Step 3. To start editing or delete the comments, the "Run" button should be clicked.

Abstracting RNA secondary structures into three views: Core, Core Plus and Shape

Step 1. In the first step of this scenario, a user should upload the RNA secondary structure provided in a DB format as described in Step 1 of *RNA secondary structure translations scenario*.

Step 2. In this step, the user can decide the type of abstractions, such as Core, Core Plus, and Shape by selecting the corresponding option.

Step 3. To start editing or delete the comments, the "Run" button should be clicked.